

Instruction Manual and Considerations for the Vesicle Distribution and Colocalization Macro

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1. Description

This macro performs a semi-automated, quantitative, and spatial analysis of vesicle distribution within individual cells. Cell selection in each image is done manually; however, these ROIs can be reused in subsequent runs. The macro then processes the images by segmenting endosomes using the StarDist plugin and categorizes these endosomes into three concentric regions around the nucleus: perinuclear, intermediate, and peripheral. Finally, it generates numerical results for the distribution and intensity of endosomes per cell and per region.

The overall workflow of image-based vesicle distribution and colocalization analysis is summarized in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: General workflow required for vesicle analysis.

2. Install requirements

This macro requires at least version 1.54e of ImageJ/FIJI, with the following features or plugins installed:

- Bio-Formats Importer for opening image files
- StarDist 2D Plugin and CSBDeep for vesicle segmentation

We recommend using FIJI, as it includes several built-in functions used by this macro.

3. StarDist threshold selection

Before running the macro, it is necessary to optimize the vesicle detection parameters of the StarDist plugin. These parameters depend on the pixel size of the images and therefore on the microscope objective used and the field of view during image acquisition.

The key parameters to be adjusted within StarDist are shown in **Figure 2**. Using a representative image from the dataset to be analyzed, each parameter should be calibrated to optimize vesicle segmentation. For further details on each parameter, please refer to the plugin's official documentation: <https://imagej.net/plugins/stardist>.

Once the optimal parameters have been determined for the images to be analysed, they can either be manually inserted into the macro code (recommended for repeated analyses with similar settings), or entered each time through the macro's interactive menu (see Section 4).

Figure 2: StarDist 2D parameter menu.

In the macro's menu, these parameters correspond to:

- percentile low = p_{Bottom} ,
- percentile high = p_{TOP} ,
- probability/score threshold = $probThres$, and
- overlap threshold = $Vesicle\ Threshold$.

4. Vesicle distribution macro interactive menu

When launching the macro, you will be prompted to select the folder containing the images, which must be in **TIF format**. Then, the **Macro Menu** will appear (**Figure 3**).

- The first section (**A**) refers to the parameters used by the macro to define the shape of the regions. These should **not be modified** under normal circumstances.
- In the second section (**B**), the optimized parameters for the **StarDist 2D** plugin can be entered. If you prefer not to input them each time, they can be hardcoded into the macro.
- The current macro is designed to work with exactly **3 defined regions**.
- The third section (**C**) allows you to select the image channel for vesicle analysis and the channel corresponding to nuclear staining.
- Finally, the fourth section (**D**) lets you define whether to **reuse previously selected ROIs** for the given images.

Figure 3: Vesicle Distribution macro set-up menu.

5. Important considerations during macro use

Below is a list of key considerations to keep in mind when using the macro:

- **Images must be in TIF format.**
- The macro is currently coded to work with **exactly three regions**.
- When defining cell ROIs, it is important to **precisely trace the full area of each cell** and to avoid selecting **overlapping cells**.
- During manual cell selection, the **POLYGON tool** must be used—this is automatically activated by the macro.
- After selecting a ROI and clicking **OK**, **wait** until the “Select cells” dialog appears again before selecting the next cell. Clicking any other window while the macro is running its internal calculations may cause an error, requiring the process to restart.
- Once cells have been selected, the macro proceeds to **region segmentation**. If an error occurs during this step, you can **re-run the macro** and select the option to **reuse ROIs** in the main menu.
- To reuse ROIs, after selecting the appropriate option in the menu, a window will prompt you to select a folder. You must select the **results folder** previously generated (e.g., *Results 2025-07-28 13h30_C1*), which includes the channel and date of the previous analysis. Within this folder, the **“04 ROIs”** subfolder contains the ROI sets that the macro will automatically load.

- To successfully reuse ROIs, **the images must be in the same order** as in the previous analysis. If any image is removed, you must also delete the corresponding .zip ROI file.
- The macro requires at least **one vesicle to be detected in each region** (perinuclear, intermediate, and peripheral). If a region—especially the **peripheral** one—lacks detected vesicles, the distribution analysis cannot be completed. In such cases, it is recommended to **exclude that cell from the analysis**.

6. Obtaining vesicle distribution results

The macro generates **three main result files**:

1. **“Analysis info”**: Contains all analysis parameters used during the session, including user-defined settings.
2. **“Endosomes per cell”**: Provides results independent of spatial regions, including:
 - Cell area
 - Total number of endosomes
 - Mean endosome area per cell
 - Mean endosome intensity per cell
3. **“Endosome distribution”**: Contains results organized **by region** (perinuclear, intermediate, and peripheral), including:
 - Percentage of endosomes in each region
 - Endosome area and intensity per region
 - Other variables mentioned above, broken down regionally

In addition, the macro creates a structured **“Results” folder**, containing several subfolders with the images generated throughout the analysis process:

1. **“Images”**: Contains the separated image channels (nucleus and vesicle channels).
2. **“Single cells”**: Contains cropped images of individual cells from the selected vesicle channel.
3. **“Single nuclei”**: Contains cropped images of the corresponding nuclei for each selected cell.
4. **“ROIs”**: Contains the cell selection ROIs for each image (used for reuse if needed).
5. **“Cell masks”**: Contains the binary masks of each selected cell.
6. **“Nucleus masks”**: Contains the binary masks of the nuclei corresponding to each selected cell.
7. **“Vesicle masks”**: Contains binary masks of vesicles per cell and per region, as well as the ROI sets used for vesicle identification.
8. **“Regions”**: Contains ROI files representing each of the three defined regions and the nucleus for each analysed cell.

7. Colocalization analysis

The colocalization macro is used to compare **two vesicular markers**. This macro must be run **after** each marker has been individually analysed using the **vesicle distribution macro**. It uses the **masks generated by the StarDist plugin** for each marker and overlays them. Colocalization is only considered when the **overlapping area is equal to or greater than 0.1 μm^2** .

Before running the macro, you must **rename the results folders** by prepending the name of the corresponding marker. For example, if *LAMP1* is in channel 1 and *CD63* is in channel 3, the folder originally named “**Results 2025-07-28 13h30_C1**” should be renamed to “**LAMP1 Results 2025-07-28 13h30_C1**”, and “**Results 2025-07-28 13h30_C3**” should be renamed to “**CD63 Results 2025-07-28 13h30_C3**”. The original date and time in the folder name must not be changed.

When the macro starts, it will ask for the folder that **contains both result folders** for each marker. It will then prompt you to select the **two channels** to analyse (in this example, C1 and C3). Additionally, colocalization analysis can also be **performed by region** (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Menu of the colocalization analysis macro.

8. Obtaining colocalization results

The macro generates a **results folder** containing two main elements:

1. A **folder with the ROIs** corresponding to the colocalization events for each individual cell.
2. A **results file** summarizing colocalization data for the **entire cell** and **by region**. This file includes:
 - The **number of colocalization events** and their **ratio relative to the total** vesicles.
 - The **number of vesicles** detected for each marker, and the **percentage** that are colocalizing
(*Number of Colocalizations / Number of vesicles for that marker [%]*).
 - The **mean area of colocalization events** per cell.

It is possible that the **sum of colocalization percentages across the three regions does not equal 100%**, since some vesicles located at the boundary between two regions may be excluded from the analysis. These percentages can be **recalculated** by dividing the **number of colocalization events per region by the total number of colocalizations detected in the entire cell**.

9. License and contact information

This plugin is licensed under the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License**, which allows use and distribution for personal or research purposes, provided that our work is properly cited. For any bugs, problems, or general question, please contact:

VesicleDistributionMacro@gmail.com

10. Citation

When using these macros, or any derivative work based on them, please cite the following DOIs:

- **Macro repository:** 10.5281/zenodo.16538283
- **Original article:** Bernaus-Esqu, M., Liu, Y., Prats, E., Estanyol, J. M., Martin, G., Calvo, M., Gigourtsi, P. A., Nguyen, M. K. L., lvarez, A. R., Zanlungo, S., Agell, N., Lu, A., Tebar, F., Enrich, C., Grewal, T., & Rentero, C. (2026). Annexin A6 controls multi-organelle contact site formation, endolysosomal positioning and remodels the StARD3 interactome. *iScience* (*In Press*).